

Supplementary Figures

Figure 1: ROC curves illustrating the performance of the models produced through KNN, utilising a combination of three distinct remote sensing datasets and two sets of training samples.

Figure 2: ROC curves illustrating the performance of the models produced through SVM, utilising a combination of three distinct remote sensing datasets and two sets of training samples.

Figure 3: ROC curves illustrating the performance of the models produced through MLP, utilising a combination of three distinct remote sensing datasets and two sets of training samples.

Figure 4: Loss graphs of the models created using MLP and different pairs of remote sensing and training datasets.

Figure 5: Accuracy graphs of the models created using MLP and different pairs of remote sensing and training datasets.

Figure 6: Loss graphs of the models created using CNN and different pairs of remote sensing and training datasets.